

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Mercuric Acetate Oxidation of 3 β -Acetoxy Methyl Betulinate

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In continuation of our work¹ on the stereochemistry of C-19 isopropenyl substituent in Hg(OAc)₂ oxidation^{2,3} products of triterpenes of lupeol series we carried out oxidation^{2,4} of 3 β -acetoxy methyl betulinate I and isolated the ester II^{2,4}, m.p. 218–19°, (α)_D+58°, whose structure has been proved unequivocally by Chopra and coworkers⁴. Catalytic hydrogenation of II afforded the reduced product IIIa, m.p. 214–16°,⁴ (α)_D+20°, which on hydrolysis by the method of Chang and Wood⁵ furnished the hydroxy acid IIIb, m.p. 287–8°, (α)_D+10°. The corresponding hydroxy ester IIIc, m.p. 198–9°, on hydrolysis by the method of Elsinger *et al.*⁶ furnished the same hydroxy acid IIIb. The latter on reesterification followed by acetylation gave back IIIa indicating that no skeletal change had taken place during hydrolysis. The hydroxy acid IIIb on pyrolytic decomposition above its melting point following Barton's method⁷ furnished the decarboxylated product assigned as IVa which has been characterised as its acetate IVb, m.p. 210–12°, (α)_D–9°, (M⁺ 454). IVa on CrO₃-Py oxidation gave the ketone IVc, m.p. 128–30°, (α)_D+31.37°. I.R. ν_{max}^{KBr} 1710 cm⁻¹ Huang-Minlon reduction of the latter compound gave the hydrocarbon IVd, m.p. 141–2° (α)_D–37.21°, (M⁺ 396) and NMR spectrum showed the absence of vinylic proton. The hydrocarbon IVd on acid isomerisation with 2N-sulfuric acid in acetic acid solution following the method of Jeger *et al.*⁸ gave a new hydrocarbon V, m.p. 193–94°, (α)_D+70° M⁺ 396, NMR spectrum showed absence of any peak attributable to vinylic proton.

1. H. N. Khastgir and S. N. Bose, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1968, No. 1, 89.
2. J. M. Allison, W. Lawrie, J. Mclean and G. R. Taylor, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 8358.
3. J. M. Allison, W. Lawrie, J. Mclean and J. M. Beaton, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 5224.
4. C. S. Chopra and (the late) D. E. White, *Tetrahedron*, 1966, 22, 897.
5. F. C. Chang and N. R. Wood, *Tetrahedron Letters*, 1964, 40, 2969.
6. F. Elsinger, J. Schreiber and A. Eschenmoser, *Helv. Chim. Acta.*, 1960, 42, 118.
7. D. H. R. Barton and C. J. W. Brooks, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 257.
8. P. Dietrich and O. Jeger, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1950, 33, 711.

The stereochemistry of C-19 isopropyl group in V was established as follows :

3 β -Acetoxy betulanic acid VI, m.p. 304–5° (Lit.⁹ m.p. 311–12.5°) was decarboxylated with Pb(OAc)₄ according to the procedure of Cambie *et al.*¹⁰ whereby a decarboxylated product VIIa and a diacetate VIII were obtained. The NMR spectra of VIIa showed a peak at δ 5.18 (vinyl proton, trisubstituted double bond). TLC analysis of the latter showed two spots very close to each other indicating that it was probably a mixture of olefins. The diacetate VIII had m.p. 207–9°, (α)_D +23.01° and its mass spectra showed molecular ion peak at M⁺ 514 and the mass fragmentation pattern¹¹ was consistent with its tentative structure assigned. Further work on the stereochemistry of the C-17 acetate group is in progress and will be reported shortly. The compound VIIa, m.p. 170–76°, (α)_D +28.27° on hydrolysis followed by CrO₃-Py oxidation gave the ketone VIIb, m.p. 145–50°, (α)_D +48.19°, I.R. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 812, 1680, 1708 cm⁻¹. Huang-Minlon reduction of the latter furnished the hydrocarbon mixture VIIc, m.p. 156–8°, (α)_D –7.00° (Lit.⁸ m.p. 153–54°, (α)_D –12.0°) which also showed a peak for vinylic proton at δ 5.2 in NMR spectrum, I.R. $\nu_{\text{max}}^{\text{KBr}}$ 812, 1680 cm⁻¹ (trisubstituted double bond). The hydrocarbon mixture was isomerised under identical conditions⁸ described above and furnished a hydrocarbon, m.p. 192–3°, (α)_D +67.2°, M⁺ 396, found to be identical in all respects (m.p., m.m.p., I.R., NMR and mass spectra comparison)

9. J. Simonsen and W. C. J. Ross, *The Terpenes*, Cambridge University Press, 1957, Vol. IV, p. 300.

10. C. R. Bennet and R. C. Cambie, *Tetrahedron*, 1967, 927.

11. H. Budzikiewicz, J. M. Wilson and C. Djerassi, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, **85**, 3788.

with hydrocarbon V (Lit.⁸ m.p. 188–9°, (α)_D+59°). It showed absence of vinylic proton in NMR spectrum and its structure V containing 13–18 double bond is consistent with its mass fragmentation pattern¹¹ (m/e 353 ($M^+ - HC \begin{matrix} \swarrow CH_3 \\ \searrow CH_3 \end{matrix}$), 204, 191, 161).

Whereas the exact stereochemistry of the C-17H cannot be ascertained the stereochemistry of C-19 isopropyl group in V is obviously as depicted in the formula as it has been derived from 3 β -acetoxy betulanic acid by reactions which precluded the possibility of any epimerisation at C-19. It follows, therefore, that the stereochemistry of the isopropenyl substituent in the oxidation product II must be *trans* with respect to the β -carbomethoxy substituent at C-17 and can now be fully expressed by structure IIa. In view of the above results the Hg(OAc)₂ oxidation product of lupeol acetate, m.p. 229–31°,² and betulin diacetate m.p. 177–78°², may be assigned structures IIb and IIc.

Satisfactory analysis were secured for the compounds described herein.*

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* Note added in proof: The α -orientation of the isopropenyl group at C-19 of emmolactone (R. A. Eade et al, *Austral. J. Chem.*, 1967, **20**, 2737) is now confirmed on the basis of our results described above.